

THE ROLE OF TELECOMMUNICATION COMPANIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTERNET OF THINGS

Aripov Sobir Khamidullayevich

Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi, Researcher

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada buyumlar internetining telekommunikasiya tarmoqlarini rivojlantirishdagi oʻrni, buyumlar internetining raqamli telekommunikasiya texnologiyalardan foydalanishning ilmiy nazariy asoslari keltirilgan. Telekommunikasiya tarmoqlarining buyumlar internetidan foydalangan holda ishda rivojlantirish texnologiyalarida qoʻllaniladigan tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan va toʻliq keltirilgan.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлена роль Интернета вещей в развитии телекоммуникационных сетей, научно-теоретические основы использования цифровых телекоммуникационных технологий Интернета вещей. Разработаны и полностью представлены рекомендации, используемые при разработке технологий телекоммуникационных сетей с использованием Интернета вещей.

Annotation. This article presents the role of the Internet of Things in the development of telecommunication networks, the scientific theoretical basis of the use of digital telecommunication technologies of the Internet of Things. The recommendations used in the development technologies of telecommunication networks using the Internet of Things are developed and fully presented.

Kalit soʻzlar. *Buyumlarlar interneti, aloqa xizmati provayderlari, raqamlashtirish, texnologiya, telekommunikatsiya kompaniyalari, tarmoq provayderlari, infratuzilma tarmoqlari, sensor texnologiyalari.*

Ключевые слова. *Интернет вещей, Поставщики услуг связи, Цифровизация, Технологии, Телекоммуникационные компании, Сетевые провайдеры, инфраструктурные сети, сенсорные технологии.*

Keywords. *Internet of Things, Communication Service Providers, Digitalization, Technology, Telecommunication companies, Network providers, infrastructure networks, sensor technologies.*

Introduction

During the rise of the Internet, communication services treated their network providers as little more than ‘dumb pipes’, providing bandwidth. The Internet of Things revolution, requiring a dramatic increase in strong, secure communication links, offers providers an opportunity to not only play a larger role but to create new value. The Internet of Things has become increasingly visible thanks to the rise of intelligent thermostats, interactive fitness trackers, and the promise of autonomous vehicles. Such technologies are compelling because they make the things around us smarter and more interactive. In the words of one commentator, we need no longer settle for dumb tools but can instead look forward to ‘enchanted objects’ (Buyya & Dastjerdi, 2016). The sensor technologies that make things ‘smart’ are only part of the Internet of Things, however, and connecting all of these devices is what makes isolated pockets of technology a network that generates and pools data in ways that

lead to valuable insights.

The main part

Communications have a central role in many Internet of Things deployments, and thanks to this companies often create value as a function of the interaction between the sensor technologies and the network layer. When linking new and legacy sensors within an Internet of Things ecosystem companies that seek to realize value from the Internet of Things need to work closely with their CSPs (Communication Service Providers).

These advantages together provide a three-layered opportunity for telecommunication companies which they can use to develop unique and differentiated strategies for the Internet of Things. The three-layered opportunity is as follows:

- Connectivity which represents the network as it interconnects billion of devices with analytics engines and massive data warehouses. In this layer of opportunity also network services are included, some of them being quality-of-service guarantees and pricing plans, and also the ability of running analytics engines in the network, managing data flows more effectively and accelerating response time;

- Life cycle management represents the ability of managing the complex cycles of devices enablement, authentication, management, maintenance and replacement. And doing this way that will ensure security of the network, device directory maintenance, and also rights management. Management like this can often take place years after the devices are installed and also spans a universe of devices which is very larger than what other suppliers would typically manage.

- Vertical solutions represent the industry-specific offers. They deliver value to the enterprises and the consumers and telecommunication companies can participate directly or choose to facilitate through the other underlying layers, the verticalsolutions that the others will provide (Tomlinson, 2000).

Only telecommunication companies have the experience and capabilities to deliver carrier-grade networks that meet compliance requirements and governance demands across a global range of regulatory schemes. They are building software-defined, virtual networks that can offer flexibility in terms of service suites and various security and performance levels. This flexibility will be essential in allowing clients to automatically self-provision when necessary or enabling integration with thirdparty systems through appropriately monitored APIs.

Telecommunication companies have deep expertise in deploying, maintaining and decommissioning the millions of devices on their networks, and this is where the opportunity in life cycle management comes from. They have expertise in managing deviceslike mobile phones and tablets which have a SIM card and link directly to an individual account. Although most of the telecommunication companies' executives are aware of this, there is an even larger opportunity that comesfrom managing the billions of devices without SIM cards and laying behind gateways, for example, controllers on factory floors and thermostats in private homes.

The focusin the early days of the Internet of Thingsis on the developing and

deploying the initial device infrastructure, and few are thinking about the scale of Internet of Things devices after deployment, and also the massive effort that will be needed to manage these billions of devices throughout their lives. Related to this, top-down estimates for commissioning, maintaining, upgrading and decommissioning these devices could be more than \$28 billion globally by 2020 (Blum, Jackson, Sinha, & Smith, 2017). Another clear opportunity for telecommunication companies is that they can develop platforms which the other industrial and consumer companies can use in order to manage their devices. A life-cycle management platform with a telecommunication company's brand which is trusted could be a significant selling asset for industrial and commercial businesses that are selling vertical solutions. Telecommunication companies can also use their advantaged position in terms of connectivity and life cycle layers to assemble vast data lakes of information. Then, they can make that information available to providers of vertical market solutions. They could also furnish infrastructure embedded in the network where analytics engines reside, whether it is operated by the telecommunication companies or by others, allowing analytics to be performed at the edge. Faster response times, and better control of which information flows or does not flow into the network will be some of the benefits.

Telecommunication companies, if well executed have a very competent position to build powerful platforms that enable vertical market solutions, and they can deploy these solutions themselves or, which may happen more frequently, they can support third-party solutions on telecommunication companies-provided platforms. Some of the vertical markets and segments where it would be logical for the telecommunication companies to enter and compete are already becoming crowded, such as smart homes, which are also drawing investments from cable TV providers, home security firms, and other tech behemoths such as Amazon , Facebook, Google, and Microsoft.

Analyzing the case study, the following objective, is completed in the practical part of this work too, in the Discussions part, where the stage at which Makedonski Telekom is in implementing IoT is identified, as being in the process of planning the implementation of IoT, same as the direction that they will follow in terms of business models and positioning on the IoT value chain. In terms of business modelsthey follow the solution integrators model which is highly advanced and if done right, will place them highly on the value chain, opening up the potential for revenue growth as the Internet of Things market matures.

When focusing on verticalsolutions, it isimportant for telecommunication companies not to underplay their hand in the two large horizontal spaces where they have the right to compete and win. In terms of scale connectivity solutions that are in the centre of the Internet of Things, only the telecommunication companies have the experience needed and, second, in terms of managing extensive directories and the life cycles of millions of devices they are also the only players with experience. Developing and managing analytics at the edge of the network and across a range of uses and industries is also where telecommunication companies have a strong position. The strengths mentioned and combined with the trusted status that telecommunication companies enjoy, leaves them uniquely qualified to facilitate the

Internet of Things solutions.

Conclusion

Network providers will have to deliver the highest-quality functionalities for the network to connect machines to machines uninterrupted, as new IoT applications are rolled out every now and then. They will have to ensure that they have a robust infrastructure that is also flexible and agile to acclimatize to the scalability and development of the new applications. Operators will have to provide uninterrupted network facilities, without any drops, at the right time and at the right speed as the need of the application dictates. IoT is changing consumers' data and connectivity demands, and because of that telecommunication companies will need to define a strategy that supports and enhances the next generation of smart devices. Strategies to increase data monetization and boosting profitability will be required. Telecommunication companies will have to offer novel value propositions and innovative pricing models that will meet the preferences of the consumers and increase the benefits to the customers.

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